

Web-based Vehicle Reservation System (VRS)

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Abstract

The Vehicle Reservation System (VRS) is a web-based application designed to streamline the vehicle reservation and approval process at the University of Sri Jayewardenepura (USJ). The existing system operates manually, requiring students and staff to submit paper-based forms with trip details. The approval process involves multiple administrative steps, including manual verifications and obtaining signatures from relevant department head, Dean and Vice chancellor. Once the approval granted, the general admin authorities inform the vehicle allocation and driver information to the department and shared information about the journey to assigned drivers. This process lacks transparency and it's difficult for users to track their reservation status in online real time. The VRS was developed to automate and optimize this process, ensuring efficient coordination, improved resource utilization, and enhanced user satisfaction. The system developed following the traditional System Development Life Cycle (SDLC) approach. The information requirements of key stakeholders were collected to identify the system functionalities. Students expected the system to provide vehicle availability for a given date, reserve vehicles, manage reservations, receive confirmations, and view their booking history. The relevant head, dean and vice chancellor expected to see all relevant information in one place and convenient approval mechanism. Further, office staff expected to assign vehicle and inform drivers after the approval granted. Key functionalities of the system include real-time tracking of vehicle availability, electronic request submission, easy approval, and role-based user access. The backend was implemented using Node.js and MongoDB, while the frontend was built with React.js and Material-UI. Testing methodologies such as unit testing, integration testing, and user acceptance testing were employed to ensure system reliability and performance. The VRS expected to eliminates paperwork, reduces administrative workload, and provides real-time tracking of reservations, significantly improving operational efficiency provided proper ICT infrastructure. This is a foundation for a mobile-based VRS system.

Keywords: *Web-based application, Vehicle Reservation System, System Development Life Cycle*